

Managing Inclusive Education Issues in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State for National Reconciliation, Integration and Economic Recovery

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Abstract

This paper examined managing inclusive education issues in public secondary schools in Rivers State for national reconciliation, integration and economy recovery. The paper identified some of the issues facing inclusive education such as attitude of teachers, funding, accessibility, facilities, motivation, curriculum and unfavorable student teacher ratio. The paper identified some of the measures for managing these issues which include among others: adequate training/ retraining of teachers; increased funding of inclusive education; improved motivation of teachers; adequate provision of teaching/learning facilities and public enlightenment. The paper concluded that without adequate attention to the management of these issues, inclusive education may fail in the realization of its policy objectives. It was therefore suggested among others that government should review teachers' training programmers in line with the teacher-quality demands of inclusive education, and all stakeholders on inclusive education should collaborate and partner with government in tackling issues facing inclusive education in Rivers State for national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery.

Keywords: Management, Inclusive Education, National Reconciliation, National Integration and Economic Recovery.

INTRODUCTION

Children with special needs or those living with disabilities are entitled to education just like the normal children. Until recently, the education of children living with disabilities was provided in an exclusive, segregated environment tagged special schools of blind, deaf and dumb and soon. Education is a major tool for personal development, socio-economic advancement, knowledge and skills empowerment, as well as poverty eradication. Every child irrespective of any physical disability deserves quality and accessible education. Hence, the commitment by governments world over to providing quality and accessible education for all. This is demonstrated in United Nations' declaration that every child irrespective of physical and mental differences has the right to education and should be offered opportunity to equitable education which will enable him/her to develop his/her capacities and skills as well hasten the process of their social integration.

Declarations like universal declaration of human rights, 1948; the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966; World Programme of Action Concerning Disabled Persons 1982; Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989; Jomtien World Conference on Education for All (EFA) 1990; Standard rules on the equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities 1993; and the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education 1994 have resulted in a stream of diverse categories of children coming into the school and classroom (Okwudire, 2019). Based on this, every classroom is made up of different type of learners with various abilities and

disabilities. Moreover, with the global pursuit of sustainable development goals, the emphasis on sustainable inclusive education has raised the bar of classroom diversity (Lennar and Jilson, 2017). In this light, inclusive education has become a global vision and a standard for providing equitable education for all children.

Nigeria adopts the policy of inclusion in her National Policy on Education. the policy stipulates the integration of special needs students into regular classrooms and free education for exceptional students at all levels. This commitment is made to equalize educational opportunities for all children, whether normal or living with any form of disability. No doubt, these are worthy goals intended to enhance the quality of special education services but much more is needed to translate the goals into reality and something achievable. Managing inclusive education in public secondary schools in Rivers State has not been easy. It is confronted with so many inherent issues. Studies have shown that inclusive public secondary schools in Rivers State lack adequate infrastructure, learning resources, well trained teachers and incentives needed to provide special needs education are some of the issues facing inclusive education.

These issues affect the implementation of inclusive education negatively and the performance of students with special needs. The researcher's interest therefore, is to examine ways inclusive education issues in public secondary schools in Rivers State can be managed for national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery.

The Concept of management

Managing is the art of management; management is defined by Ikekwo aba And Maduikwe (2016) as the total system of organization, getting organizational personnel to accomplish their work so as to achieve organization's objectives. In practical sense, management deals with the delegation of authority or functions to subordinates and gets the job done effectively.

Organization and utilization of the human and material resources in an organization for the attainment of set objectives. It is a social process which is designed to ensure corporate participation, intervention and involvement of people towards the achievement of a given or predetermined objective. In the field of education, management can be described as the art of working, particularly through; people for the attainment of the broad education goals (Wicks,2009).

Management of inclusive education issues may be seen as the application of management principles in handling and addressing issues arising from the adoption of inclusive education system. A super-ordinate does this activity by applying managerial functions such as planning, organizing, directing and controlling the affairs of the organization through the subordinates. The adoption of inclusive education needs to be properly planned for effective implementation. Necessary preparations and arrangements should be made to facilitate its execution and government and all the stakeholders in inclusive education should be pro-active in handling issues arising from the adoption of this system of education.

Concept of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a system of education where all learners especially children, despite their individual differences like socio-economic backgrounds, religion and other diversities are allowed to study together, and are welcomed by their community schools in classes that are appropriate to their age groups (Okeke & Wenenda, 2019). Inclusive education is an emerging approach, philosophy and global movement which accepts that all children regardless of their ability, disability, cast, creed and so on can learn and should learn together in a mainstream school (Sarkar, 2017). It is a model that values the diversity in the abilities, competencies, behaviour and personalities of children. Thus, inclusive education mandates that all children regardless of physical, social, cultural, cognitive differences should be educated in the neighborhood schools accessible to all children in the area. Understanding of inclusive education according to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016) requires the underlying concepts of normalization, zero rejection policy, least

restrictive environment and integration. According to Garuba (2003) inclusions is a step further in mainstreaming, as it presents a means by which a school attempts to respond to all pupils as individuals, by reconsidering and structuring its curricular organization and provision, and allocating resources to enhance equality of opportunity. In other words, inclusive education does not simply mean placement of children with disability in general education classes. There are reforms to be carried out in the schools to functionally accommodate learners with special needs. These reforms may include human (change in attitudes to accept and respect diversity), physical (to enhance access to the school's critical infrastructures in order to achieve barrier-free school environment) pedagogical (to emphasize inclusive instructional strategies that focus on divers needs and backgrounds of all learners), instructional team (to provide for regular, special teachers and teacher aids); and conceptual(to institute ways of regulating inter-personal relationship in the school) among others.

Inclusive education is of great relevance in national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery because it ensures that no group of children is marginalised educationally. It brings consolation and hope to all he children of school age, thus providing a sense of belonging to them. According to Global partnership in education (2018), effective management of inclusive education for national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery demands that:

1. Government should make sure that children with disabilities are not excluded from the general education, they should have access to an inclusive, quality, free primary and secondary education on equal babies with other children.
2. Government should make sure that pupils living with disabilities receive the support they need within the general education system to improve effective education.
3. Government should ensure that reasonable accommodation of the student's requirement is provided.
4. Government should enhance the learning of Braille and sign language, ensuring that the education of students, and in particular those who are blind, deaf or deaf and dumb is given or carried out in the most appropriate language, modes and means of communication for the individual and environments, which maximize academic and social integration.

In line with UNESCO (2015), the fundamental principle of inclusive education is that all children should learn together, wherever possible, regardless of any difficulties or differences they may have. This system of

education recognizes and responds to the diverse needs of their students, accommodating both different styles and rates of learning and ensuring quality education for all, through appropriate curricula, organizational arrangements, teaching strategies, resource use and partnership with their communities in compliance with global best practices.

Inclusive schools ensure continuum of support and services to match the continuum of special needs encountered in every school. Within inclusive schools, children with special needs receive whatever extra support they may require to ensure their effective education. Inclusive education has become the most effective means for building solidarity between children with special needs and their peers according to Urite, Wertson and Diannet (2015). This enhances national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery.

National Reconciliation

National reconciliation are means or processes of establishing national unity in countries or societies confronted with political crisis. It is means of giving a sense of belonging to all the citizens of a particular country. National reconciliation refers to efforts made to address the harms, injustices, marginalization's and grievances caused by various policies and programmes of government. Over the years, we have experienced in equalities in the provision of access to education. Those living with disabilities have faced various challenges in their attempts to access education in Nigeria. Inclusive education is part of the measures for addressing marginalization of some group of pupils from access to education.

National Integration

National integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different castes, religions, regions and speak different language, we recognize that we are all one. National integration encourages patriotism and nationalism. National reconciliation will facilitate national integration. It is therefore necessary to bridge all the gaps and correct all the imbalances in the provision of access to education for all citizens at all levels.

Economic recovery

Economic recovery has to do with the various measures taken to revive an ailing economy. It comes after a period of economic downturn or recession. Economic recovery is associated with growth indicators like improved GDP, reduced unemployed rates, low exchange rates, high foreign direct investments and improved infrastructural developments. Adequate management of

inclusive education issues will enhance access to quality education to all citizens, empowerment of people, and their rate of productivity. This has positive effect on economic recovery.

Issues in the Implementation of Inclusive Education

One of the core issues facing the implementation and achievement of inclusive education in Rivers State and most other parts of Nigeria is the attitude of teachers and normal children towards children living with disabilities. In reality, attitude shapes the way both the society and policy makers perceive persons who may deviate in certain characteristics from the norm. the attitude towards children living with disabilities is fundamentally critical. It manifests itself in the process of special education legislation and policy making, as well as implementation of such frameworks. Attitudinal barrier has remained a serious issue in the practice of inclusive education. According to Lukar and Dainte (2016) attitudes are a collection of beliefs, feelings, values and dispositions which characterize the way we think, feel about certain people or situations. Supporting this view Harvey (2013) further explains that attitudes are made up of the groups of feelings, likes, dislikes, behavioral intentions, thoughts and ideas we have about other people and things we encounter in our everyday lives. It appears we are gradually appreciating diversity of human abilities and characteristics, but not without reservations such that this still possess a great barrier in the practice of inclusive education.

The attitude of teachers, learners and parents who are living without disabilities towards pupils/students living with disabilities matters a lot and has been seen as a decisive factor in making schools more inclusive. These negative attitudes prevent equity in educational service provision.

Funding is another serious issue limiting the effectiveness of inclusive education in Rivers State. Adequate funding is required to recruit skilled manpower, provide adequate classroom blocks and environment, procure and maintain infrastructural facilities, instructional materials and to cope with emergencies arising from expansion or increase in special needs education. Funding of education in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular has suffered a big setback over the years. It has been a big obstacle in the achievement of educational goals, especially in special needs education service delivery. According to Mekoyor (2017), special needs education like the entire education sector is being grossly under funded by governments. It is pathetic to note that special needs education which requires more funds when compared to regular education receives far less and has no specific funding formula and source, and

it is often attended to when there is an overflow of resources from the budget so regular education.

There is also the issue of accessibility. Accessibility refers to the ease of reaching goods, services, activities and destinations, within the school environment. Accessibility barriers in inclusive schools according to Okwudire (2016) are grouped into social barriers, psychological barriers, and structural barriers. Accessibility is a critical indicator of inclusive education that reveals the extent to which there is equitable access to educational facilities, environment, services and curriculum (UNESCO, 2011). Today, there is global focus on personalized learning; equal access therefore means that students of all abilities should have access or opportunities to learn, move and benefit from available services and facilities equally. In other words, accessible schools benefit the entire community, facilitating growth of the whole social structure.

The challenge of accessing facilities and services within inclusive schools by persons living with disabilities is on the increase due to the deterioration and wearing out of existing facilities, as well as increase in school enrolment. Providing accessible school buildings alone does not guarantee adequate access to education for all children (UNESCO, 2015). The learners have diverse educational needs according to their peculiarities. Some may need highly structured environment with considerable individual attention. Others may require sophisticated equipment or specialist staff, while yet others need little more than minor adjustments to normal schooling.

To avoid barriers of having access to education in an inclusive setting, the architecture, support services and curriculum processes must have reasonable accommodation catering for individual needs of each child are equally required alongside addressing the general accessibility needs. Accessible features such as ramps, wider doorways, and accessible toilets etc are required in inclusive schools. If a child with special needs does not have access to general curriculum and relevant support a service, such a child is deprived the right to education.

We also have the teacher factors affecting inclusive education. One of the serious issues facing the implementation of inclusive education is teachers' inadequate knowledge/competence in classroom management and pedagogical accommodation of diverse learners with variegated physical, mental and learning characteristics in the same classroom. According to Ebene (2016), the incompetence of teachers in managing and fulfilling pedagogical obligations within inclusive classrooms manifest in a range of social and psychological barriers which preempts the actualization of inclusive education. These

social and psychological barriers result in negative attitudes and other problems. Inadequate motivation of teachers by government, parents and the entire members of the society is another issue facing inclusive education's effectiveness.

Teachers are the implementers of innovations in education. without adequate motivation of teachers, it will be difficult for inclusive education to be effectively implemented. Supporting this view Eleyeji(2018) opined that teachers makethe difference between paper and practice in any education system. Succinctly put, inclusive education cannot be successfully achieved without teachers who are adequately motivated. Teachers are regarded as the major stakeholders in the implementation of any educational policy. They occupy a central role in the quest for inclusive practice in schools. Since they constitute such a core component in the process, the extent to which they are motivated to carry out their duties becomes psycho-emotionally crucial.

The education of children with special needs demands a lot of responsibility even at personal levels from teachers. The inability of these teachers to be motivated by providing needed incentives result to negative attitudes towards the education of special needs children in the regular classes.

We equally have curriculum issue facing the implementation of inclusive education for national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery. Just as the environment must be accessible to students with disabilities, the curriculum must facilitate inclusive education too. General educators must be willing to work with inclusion specialists to make modifications in classroom and homework assignments. The teachers should be flexible in how students learn and demonstrate knowledge and understanding. Written work, for example should be limited if students cannot write and can accomplish the same or similar learning objective through a different method. Curriculum practice in Nigeria has not still made adequate provision for inclusive education. Other issues are limited knowledge about inclusive education among educators; unfavorable student-teacher ratio; and inadequate teacher preparation.

Management of Issues in Inclusive Education

According to Nzewi (2019); Nwankwo and Nnatu (2018), managing issues in inclusive education would require the following:

1. Ensuring that educators such as teachers and head teachers have adequate training, flexibility and resources to teach learners with various needs and learning styles.
2. Making sure that schools enjoy adequate and sustainable financial support so that all activities and

- services are fully inclusive.
3. Empowering parents to assert their children's right to education in inclusive settings.
 4. Enabling the entire community, including mainstream and special educators, social workers, parents and students to work together and participate in the design, delivery and monitoring of education, there by reframing inclusive education as a shared responsibility.
 5. Holding government accountable for implementing anti-discriminatory legislation, legal mandates for inclusion and policies to remove barriers.

Adequate management of teacher issues in inclusive education would require adequate training and retraining of teachers. Supporting this view Sparks (2017) states that research and experiences recognize that high quality ongoing professional development that deepens teachers' professional knowledge and pedagogical skills; provide opportunities for practice, research and reflection, and assists in the goal to remain up-to-date in pedagogical practices for children living with disabilities. Equipping teachers with appropriate knowledge and skills will improve their performances in inclusive classrooms.

Providing the right motivation for teachers is equally crucial and necessary in the delivery of quality inclusive education. This will help to improve teachers' attitudes, deployment, of good pedagogical practices for children with special needs. Inclusive education is faced with a lot of inadequacies of teachers and teaching resources. Over coming this challenge or managing it would demand a proactive effort from all stakeholders in inclusive education. There is need for an integrated funding of the programme to facilitate the actualization of the objectives. Governments, parents, organizations and international agencies should all be involved in the funding of inclusive education. Through integrated funding strategies, stakeholders would ensure the generation of adequate funds needed for effective implementation of inclusive education.

Managing an equitable inclusive education setting entails that school services and facilities for the learners are available on an equal term to persons with disabilities and are responsive to their needs. Many students with disabilities in inclusive schools do not maximally benefit from educational provision because the accessibility component is grossly neglected in the policy formulation and implementation of inclusive education. In order to manage this situation, it is very necessary that the environment and services within inclusive schools are adequately planned, developed, management and executed in an equitable manner

(Adeyinka, 2013). By so doing, the interest of all the learners will be considered, and the facilities, services and the entire environment will be beneficial to all and reach all sections of the community including persons living disabilities with.

Attitudinal issues facing inclusive education should be tackled through attitudinal changes. Changing negative attitudes from individuals, the community to the society against learners with special needs is very challenging and involves great efforts from the schools, government and relevant agencies. Changing the attitudes of the school and the society involves disabusing their minds of existing belief structure and instilling in them positive attitudes. According to Ekor and Ekemiji (2015) people have negative attitudes towards people living with disabilities as a result of ignorance and lack of knowledge on the reasons for their disabilities. Managing this situation requires public enlightenment. Government agencies, churches, mosques, civil society organizations, elites, political organization and all non-governmental organizations should join efforts in changing the attitude of people towards those living with disabilities. People should be made to see ability in people living with disabilities.

Formulation and Enforcement of relevant policies:

It has been observed that Inclusive education has not yielded the desired results in Nigeria even with the formulation of inclusive education policy. According to Bahandri (2017), any inclusive education blue print without legal backing is equal to mere statements of intent with no legal capacity to litigate for justice. Inclusive education policy in Nigeria lacks legal backing and mechanism with which government or any individual can be held responsible in the case of any infringement. Appropriate legal frameworks should be promulgated and enforced for effective management of inclusive education that will promote national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery.

Managing inclusive education issues in public secondary schools in Rivers State for national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery would require building partnerships with relevant stakeholders. Partnerships play an essential role in successful schools, often providing supports and resources to meet staff, family and students needs that go beyond what is typically available through school. Partnership is a means of solving problems through shared responsibility by the stakeholders. To ensure the success of inclusive education, which is in line with global best practices, it is necessary for schools to collaborate and partner with children, families, parents, civil society, communities, governments, NGO's/DPO's, UN agencies, universities, media, and the

CONCLUSION

Inclusive education is a welcome development directed towards providing quality education to every child with or without disability. This lofty education policy which, if successfully implemented will enhance national reconciliation, integration and economic recovery is faced with a lot of issues such as: attitudinal, teachers, funding, accessibility, and facilities issues. Adequate attention should be paid to the management of these issues through proper training and retraining of teachers, publican lighten mention the need for change of attitude towards those living with disabilities, improved funding, adequate provision of relevant facilities, collaboration and partnership with relevant stake holder sand soon. Without paying attention to these issues and effectively managing them, there is no doubt that inclusive education policy may fail to achieve its targeted objectives in Rivers State.

Suggestions/ way forward

The researcher thereby suggests the following

1. Government should formulate legal frameworks to strengthen inclusive education policy in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Government should review teachers' training programmes so that it matches with the teacher quality demands of inclusive education programme in the state.
3. Government should organize professional development programmes for teachers in Rivers state to equip them with the pedagogical knowledge, and Skills required for inclusive education.
4. All stakeholders on inclusive education should collaborate and partner with government in tackling the issues facing inclusive education programme in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

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